

LEGAL REGULATION OF THE PROCEDURE FOR ADMISSION TO THE STATE PUBLIC SERVICE IN REPUBLIC UZBEKISTAN

Avezova Eleonora Paraxatovna

Lecturer at Tashkent state University of law
Department of Administrative and Financial law

E.mail: avezova.eleonora@tsul.uz

Elenavezova637@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9254-4029>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7402755>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th November 2022

Accepted: 28th November 2022

Online: 30th November 2022

KEY WORDS

State civil service, competition, types of competition, necessary elements of the competition, conditions of the competition, competition stages, competition commission.

One of the essential features of a developed state is the public apparatus of power, which ensures the fulfillment of the tasks and functions assigned to the state. Undoubtedly, a lot depends on the productive activity of public authorities in the person of its state civil servants, namely: conducting a successful domestic and foreign policy, economic development and prosperity of the country.

Currently, the State civil service is one of the key institutions of the state. It should be emphasized that the state civil service is understood as a type of public service, which is a professional paid activity of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure the exercise of the powers of state bodies in the positions of the state civil service [1].

The analysis of the institute of State civil service in the system of national legislation shows that it is a multidimensional,

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the analysis of the essential features of the competition as a tool that ensures the ordering of public relations that develop in the process of selecting candidates for appointment to public civil service positions. Based on the study of the best practices of foreign countries, was developed a proposal for the participation of a qualified psychologist as part of the competition commission to determine the psychological qualities of applicants for admission to the state public service.

complex and legal phenomenon, the reform of which is still not finished today. After all, our state has set the goal of providing a personnel reserve, improving the level of qualifications and authority of state civil servants. Consequently, it is impossible to achieve the set goals without a proper regulatory framework regulating the procedure for admission to the state civil service [3].

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the personnel policy and the state civil service" № UP-5843, it is noted that, despite the ongoing large-scale reforms, a number of problems and shortcomings remain, leading to insufficient provision of state bodies and organizations with qualified specialists [2]. The author believes that the main mechanism ensuring the replenishment of public authorities by state civil servants

who have a sufficient level of qualifications, competence, professional qualities and personal qualities is a competition.

Consideration of the concept of competition should begin with an analysis of the position of D.V. Romanov, who believes that the introduction of the competition as a stage of selection and formation of a personnel team of qualified specialists will allow the competition to develop further as a democratic direction of candidate selection [4].

Agreeing with the opinion of D.V. Romanov, it is necessary to pay attention to the work of A.N. Bashirov, who puts forward the position that the development of a competitive method of election to the position of state civil servants will inevitably lead to an expanded use of the personnel selection procedure [5].

At the same time, it is impossible not to ignore the work of L.V. Zaitseva, in which she interprets the competition as a process of evaluating candidates using appropriate techniques [6].

As for the opinions of other scientists such as V.Yu. Alexandrova, they consider the competition as a way of creating labor relations between an employee and an employer [7].

Summarizing the above, the author of this article comes to the conclusion that the competition should be understood as a tool that ensures the ordering of relations that develop in the process of selecting decent, qualified and competent personnel for the vacant position of the state civil service.

Having considered the significance of the competition from the concept of law, it is advisable to proceed to the analysis of its essence from a regulatory position.

It should be noted that the main regulatory act regulating the procedure for admission

to the state civil service is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Civil Service". Article 27 of this Law stipulates that admission to the state civil service is carried out by appointing a candidate for the position of the state civil service on the basis of a competition, with the exception of holding positions of the state civil service, for which the legislation provides a different procedure [1].

Speaking about the essence of holding a competition for admission to the state civil service, it is important to emphasize the purpose that state bodies provide for when making a decision on holding a competition.

The main goal, in our opinion, is to attract specialists of the highest professional level to the state civil service, who have the necessary practical skills and abilities, as well as socio-moral attitudes for the most effective implementation of official duties and, accordingly, state functions of a particular public administration body in which a civil servant will carry out official activities.

In addition to the above, competitive procedures also perform a number of tasks that contribute to:

- raising the prestige of the position;
- attracting more candidates;
- improving the objectivity of the decision on hiring;
- democratization and openness of the personnel management sphere;
- introduction of new technologies of personnel work;
- intensification of the collection of personal information for planning work with hired candidates;
- formation of teams[8].

Having analyzed the competition from the standpoint of science and legislation, the

author of the study considers it necessary to consider the elements required for conducting the competitive procedure when appointing a candidate for the position of state civil service.

First of all, the most necessary element of the competitive procedure is considered to be applicants who put up their candidacy for a competition to occupy a vacant position.

The second element, in terms of importance, is the competition commission, which, in accordance with a regulatory act or regulation regulating the activities of a state body, is given the right to choose methods and techniques for conducting the competition.

When deciding on the competence of a candidate for a public civil service position, mechanisms for assessing the individual merits and qualities of contestants are of particular importance, therefore, they act as the third element of the competitive procedure.

And finally, the last element of the tender procedure is a mechanism for informing participants and other interested parties about the progress and results of the competition [9].

Based on the analysis of the concept, essence, necessary elements and the purpose of the competition, it can be said that competitive procedures are one of the tools that ensure not only transparency and openness of the procedures for admission to the civil service, but also increases the objectivity of the decision to accept a candidate for the civil service.

The study of foreign experience in working with personnel shows that the competitive procedure for filling positions of the state civil service is divided into two stages.

In the UK, citizens who wish to enter the civil service in the police, submit an application to the head of the police station, after which they are interviewed, and the applicants' documents are studied. After successful completion of the interview, a decision is made on the admission of citizens who have expressed a desire to serve in the police to the competition tests or on refusal of admission to the competitive tests.

When applying for service in the British police, the loyalty of a citizen to the existing political system is considered an important requirement. There is an age limit. A candidate for service must be at least 18 years old and not older than 30 years, since it is believed that it is at this age that a person is most trained and at the same time least inclined to change his place of service and type of activity [10].

France also belongs to the States in which competitive beginnings of filling positions of the state civil service are a priority, including when recruiting for the police. When hiring for public service in France, the principle of equal access for all citizens applies, discrimination on the basis of sex is prohibited. At the same time, if a candidate's political views are incompatible with the position he is applying for (for example, harsh criticism of government policy), he will be refused employment [11].

In this case, there is a clear similarity with the requirements for candidates for admission to the civil service in the UK. In general, there are five main conditions for admission to participate in the competition for a civil service position: French citizenship, possession of political rights, compliance with laws, a positive attitude to

the laws on military service, as well as physical fitness for this job.

A distinctive feature of the procedure for admission to the German civil service is that employees are selected on the basis of a set of criteria necessary for its performance, which include: stress resistance, motivation for official activity, compliance with the level of knowledge of the position intended for replacement, and a number of others.

Promotion and career growth for a civil servant in Germany are associated with the fulfillment of a number of detailed regulated conditions, which are different for different levels and categories of service. According to the generally accepted rule, a civil servant must pass an exam to be promoted. For each position, certain requirements are set for the candidate's level of education. The peculiarities of public service in Germany include long periods of internship and preparatory service [12].

In Japan, government employees include officials, persons working at state-owned enterprises, employees of state railways, television workers, public schools, military personnel, as well as police officers. The principle of equal access of citizens to public service applies. Only a Japanese citizen can apply for the position of a civil servant.

Appointment to the civil service is made on the basis of competitive examinations, which can be conducted both in written and oral form. When promoted, officials in Japan also take exams confirming their professional qualifications [13].

The study of the experience of the above-mentioned foreign countries shows that the conduct of competitive procedures for admission to the service mainly consists of

2 stages, at each of which the competition commission performs certain tasks to verify that the individual qualities of the candidate meet the requirements for the position of a state civil servant.

At the first stage of the competitive selection, measures are implemented that include the tasks of verifying the completeness and reliability of the information provided by applicants for participation in the competition, as well as checking the compliance of the candidate's professional qualities with the requirements for education and service experience or other work activity in the specialty for a specific vacant position.

After studying the information provided by the candidates, the competition commission decides on the choice of methods and techniques for selecting candidates. At this stage, the decision on the place and duration of this stage is made by a representative of public administration bodies, who acts as an employer. The most common and often used in practice methods of assessing the professional and personal qualities of a candidate are an interview with a candidate, a questionnaire of a candidate, discussion group meetings, solving test tasks [11].

At the same time, it should be noted that the method of selection of candidates for the state civil service chosen by the competition commission should be focused on those requirements that apply to a specific vacant position and ensure the selection of specialists who can most effectively exercise the powers of such a position.

Taking into account that the procedure for conducting competitions for admission to the state civil service in the Republic of

Uzbekistan has not yet been fixed by regulatory acts, and also taking into account the fact that state civil servants are required to have such qualities as stress resistance, the author of this article suggests the participation of a qualified psychologist as part of the competition commission, since only a qualified

psychologist can determine the suitability of employee for further service.

Guided by the above, it can be concluded that in all democratic legal states, a scientifically developed, clearly regulated regulatory procedure for admission to the state civil service serves to form a highly qualified personnel of the state apparatus.

References:

1. Закон Республики Узбекистан «О государственной гражданской службе» № ЗРУ №788 от 08.08.2022 <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6146009>.
2. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по кардинальному совершенствованию кадровой политики и государственной гражданской службы» №УП-5843 от 03.10.2019 <https://lex.uz/docs/4549993>.
3. Paraxatovna, Avezova Eleonora. "РОЛЬ ТИПОВЫХ ПРАВИЛ ПОВЕДЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ СЛУЖАЩИХ ПРИ БОРЬБЕ С КОРРУПЦИЕЙ." *Conferencea* (2022): 188-190.
4. Александрова В.Ю., Попов С.И., Гусарская Т.А. Политика совершенствования аттестации государственных гражданских служащих // Вопросы политологии. 2018. № 10. С. 740.
5. Баширов А.Н. Право граждан на равный доступ к государственной гражданской службе и механизм его реализации // Вестник Московского университета. 2015. №1. С.22.
6. Зайцева Л.В. Обеспечение реализации принципа равного доступа к государственной гражданской службе // Вестник Тюменского государственного университета. 2013. №3. С. 92.
7. Романова Д.В. Конкурсный отбор персонала государственной гражданской службы: понятие и особенности нормативного регулирования// Традиции государственного управления: проблемы и перспективы сборник материалов круглого стола.2014. №6. С. 33.
8. Paraxatovna, Avezova Eleonora. "ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF COMBATING CORRUPTION IN THE PUBLIC SERVICE." *E Conference Zone*. 2022.
9. Романова Д.В. Конкурсный отбор персонала государственной гражданской службы: понятие и особенности нормативного регулирования// Традиции государственного управления: проблемы и перспективы сборник материалов круглого стола.2014. №6. С. 33
10. Шоисломова, Ситора Саидовна. "Понятие и виды дисциплинарных взысканий в трудовом законодательстве Республики Узбекистан." *Science and Education* 3.3 (2022): 1184-1192.
11. https://studbooks.net/1312829/menedzhment/konkursnyy_nabor_personala_rabotu.

12. Авезова, Элеонора Парахатовна. "ПОНЯТИЕ, ЗНАЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕЛИ СУДЕБНОГО САНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ В УГОЛОВНОМ СУДОПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ." *Студенческий вестник* 15-2 (2021): 39-40.
 13. Шоисломова, Ситора Саидовна. "Процессуальные особенности привлечения работника к дисциплинарной ответственности по законодательству зарубежных стран." *Science and Education* 3.5 (2022): 1864-1871.
 14. Yusupov S. LEGAL REGULATION OF PARLIAMENTARY CONTROL OVER THE STATE BUDGET //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2021. – С. 159-163.
 15. Yusupov S. SOME ISSUES OF PARLIAMENTARY CONTROL OVER THE STATE BUDGET IN THE CONSTITUTION LEGAL ORDER //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2021. – С. 107-110.
 16. Sardorbek Y. ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS IN THE PROCESS OF PARLIAMENTARY CONSIDERATION OF BUDGET EXECUTION REPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.4 Legal sciences.
 17. Юсупов С. Б. COVID-19 ПАНДЕМИЯСИ ДАВРИДА ДАВЛАТ БЮДЖЕТИ УСТИДАН ПАРЛАМЕНТ НАЗОРАТИНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ АСОСЛАРИ //ЮРИСПРУДЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
 18. Bakhodirovich Y. S. International Legal Bases of Parliamentary Control Over the State Budget: On the Example of Inter-Parliamentary Institutions //International Journal of Development and Public Policy. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 130-134.
 19. Юсупов С. Б. ДАВЛАТ БЮДЖЕТИ УСТИДАН ПАРЛАМЕНТ НАЗОРАТИ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШНИНГ УСТУВОР ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ //ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2021. – №. SPECIAL 3.
 20. Sardorbek Y. ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS IN THE PROCESS OF PARLIAMENTARY CONSIDERATION OF BUDGET EXECUTION REPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.4 Legal sciences.
 21. Goziev, K. (2021, December). PRINCIPLES OF TAX LEGISLATION. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 9-12).
 22. Goziev, K. (2021, November). DEMOCRATIZATION OF STATE POWER AND GOVERNANCE IS AN IMPORTANT CONDITION FOR THE PRINCIPLE OF SEPARATION OF POWERS. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 124-132).
 23. Жураев, А. Н. (2021). REPRESENTATIVE INSTITUTE FOR THE PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS AND LEGAL INTERESTS OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN ENSURING THE RULE OF LAW. *ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ*, (SPECIAL 1).
 24. Жураева, А. Б. (2020). PRIOR RIGHTS IN TRADEMARK IN UZBEKISTAN, CHINA AND GERMANY COMPARATIVE STUDY. *ЮРИСПРУДЕНЦИЯ*, 1(1).
 25. Akhrorov, A. (2021). ENVIRONMENTAL CONTROL OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION BODIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.
 26. Khudoyberganova, M. . (2021). THE ROLE OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND CURRENT RESEARCH CONFERENCES*, 1(1), 147-152.
- Retrieved from
<https://usajournalshub.com/conferences/index.php/iscrc/article/view/200>

27. Исаева, Ф. Б. (2021). ДАВЛАТ ХИЗМАТЧИСИНИ АТТЕСТАЦИЯДАН ЎТКАЗИШ ВА УНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ ОҚИБАТЛАРИ. ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ, (SPECIAL 1).
28. Farida Isaeva. (2021). LEGAL BASIS FOR EVALUATING AND CERTIFYING THE ACTIVITIES OF A CIVIL SERVANT. *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*, 1(01), 100–106. Retrieved from <http://orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/161>
29. Исаева Фарида (2020). Роль Конституции в реформировании государственной службы в Республике Узбекистан и создании ее правовой основы. *Review of law sciences*, 1 (Спецвыпуск), 33-39. doi: 10.24412/2181-919X-2020-1-33-39
30. Khumoyun, S. (2021) "CONCEPT AND PURPOSES OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN THE ASPECT OF LABOR LAW: CONCEPT AND PURPOSES OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN THE ASPECT OF LABOR LAW", *TSUL Legal Report International electronic scientific journal*, 2(1), pp. 118-126. Available at: <https://www.legalreport.tsul.uz/index.php/journal/article/view/52> (Accessed: 2November2021).
31. Feruza Salixova. (2021). THE ROLE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN CUSTOMS. *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*, 1(01), 118–123. Retrieved from <http://orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/165>
32. Салихова, Ф. Т. (2021). БОЖХОНА НАЗОРАТИНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШДА КОНТРАФАКТ ТОВАРЛАРНИ АНИҚЛАШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ, (SPECIAL 1)
33. Soyipov, K. (2021). ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE REDUCTION OF STATE GOVERNANCE IN THE ECONOMIC SPHERE. In *Multidiscipline Proceedings of Digital Fashion Conference* (Vol. 1, No. 2).
34. Khumoyun, S. (2021). CONCEPT AND PURPOSES OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN THE ASPECT OF LABOR LAW: CONCEPT AND PURPOSES OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN THE ASPECT OF LABOR LAW. *TSUL Legal Report International electronic scientific journal*, 2(1), 118-126.
35. Ниязова, Н., Ардатова, Е., & Сойипов, Х. (2021). Обучение языкам как основа развития юридической науки и образования. *Общество и инновации*, 2(2), 137-143.
36. Juraeva, A. (2021, November). STATE RESPONSIBILITY FOR COVID-19 IS CHINA LIABLE. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 151-158). Жураева, А. Б. (2020). PRIOR RIGHTS IN TRADEMARK IN UZBEKISTAN, CHINA AND GERMANY COMPARATIVE STUDY. *ЮРИСПРУДЕНЦИЯ*, 1(1).
37. Ахроров, А. (2021). ТЕНДЕНЦИИ УПРОЩЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕДУР ЛИЦЕНЗИРОВАНИЯ И РАЗРЕШЕНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН. *Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA*.
38. Akhrorov, A. (2021, April). ENVIRONMENTAL CONTROL OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION BODIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*.
39. Abduvaliev, M. (2020). Invalidity of agreements in civil law-an analysis of the experience of Uzbekistan and Japan. *TSUL Legal Report International electronic scientific journal*, 1(1).

40. Maksudjon, A. (2020). DEVELOPING NORM CREATIVITY IN THE PROCESS OF ENSURING THE RULE OF LAW IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Review of law sciences, 1*(Спецвыпуск).
41. Maksudjon, A. (2020). CONSTITUTIONAL CONCEPTS OF THE RIGHT TO FREEDOM OF MOVEMENT FROM ONE PLACE TO ANOTHER AND LEGAL RESTRICTIONS (EXAMPLE OF REGISTRATION SYSTEM). *Review of law sciences, (4)*, 6-9.
42. Ғозиев, К. (2022). ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМНИ ТАШКИЛ ҚИЛИШ БЎЙИЧА АЙРИМ РИВОЖЛАНГАН ДАВЛАТЛАР ТАЖРИБАСИ. *Involta Scientific Journal, 1(4)*, 3-15.
43. Газиев, К. (2022). Ўзбекистонда олий таълим муассасаларини бошқариш ва ташкил этишининг ҳуқуқий жиҳатлари. *Общество и инновации, 3(6/S)*, 131-155.
44. Goziev, K. (2022). THE ESSENCE OF THE LAW ON BANK SECRET OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *World Bulletin of Management and Law, 12*, 70-72.
45. Paraхatovna, A. E. (2022). РОЛЬ ТИПОВЫХ ПРАВИЛ ПОВЕДЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ СЛУЖАЩИХ ПРИ БОРЬБЕ С КОРРУПЦИЕЙ. *Conferencea*, 188-190.
46. Авезова, Э. П. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВИДОВ И ФОРМ КОРРУПЦИОННЫХ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЙ НА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЕ. *SIYOSATSHUNOSLIK, HUQUQ VA XALQARO MUNOSABATLAR JURNALI, 1(6)*, 91-94.
47. Авезова, Э. П. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВИДОВ И ФОРМ КОРРУПЦИОННЫХ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЙ НА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЕ. *SIYOSATSHUNOSLIK, HUQUQ VA XALQARO MUNOSABATLAR JURNALI, 1(6)*, 91-94.
48. Авезова, Э. П. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВИДОВ И ФОРМ КОРРУПЦИОННЫХ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЙ НА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЕ. *SIYOSATSHUNOSLIK, HUQUQ VA XALQARO MUNOSABATLAR JURNALI, 1(6)*, 91-94.
49. Ражабова, К. Қ. (2022). САЙЛОВ КОМИССИЯЛАРИ, УЛАРНИНГ ХАТТИ-ҲАРАКАТЛАРИ (ҚАРОРЛАРИ) ТУШУНЧАСИ ВА ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.
50. Ражабова, Карима Қаҳрамоновна (2022). САЙЛОВ КОМИССИЯЛАРИНИНГ ХАТТИ-ҲАРАКАТЛАРИ (ҚАРОРЛАРИ) ЮЗАСИДАН НИЗОЛАШИШ ТЎҒРИСИДАГИ ИШЛАРНИ СУДДА КЎРИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАР. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (Special Issue 23)*, 556-563. doi: 10.24412/2181-1784-2022-23-556-563
51. Mavjuda, X., & Asgarov, M. (2022). AHOLINI DORI VOSITALARI VA TIBBIYOT BUYUMLARI BILAN TA'MINLASHDA DAVLAT BOSHQARUVINING ROLI. *Involta Scientific Journal, 1(4)*, 83-106.